

Sustain Sahel

Project Title: SustainSAHEL - SYNERGISTIC USE AND PROTECTION OF NATURAL RESOURCES FOR RURAL LIVELIHOODS THROUGH SYSTEMATIC INTEGRATION OF CROPS, SHRUBS AND LIVESTOCK IN THE SAHEL

Project number: 861974

Project Acronym: SustainSAHEL

Type: Research & Innovation action

Work program topics addressed: SFS-35-2019-2020
Sustainable Intensification in Africa

Deliverable No D6.2: Ration calculation table with nutritional details on shrub-foliage containing diets

Due date of deliverable: 31 Dec 2021 (M16)

Actual submission date: 21 Dec 2021 (M16)

Actual resubmission date: 28 June 2022 (M22)

Version: v2 (pilot, working document)

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D6.2 Ration calculation table

Project ref. number	Grant Agreement No 861974
Project title	SustainSAHEL

Deliverable title	Ration calculation table with nutritional details on shrub-foliage containing diets
Deliverable number	D6.2
Deliverable version	1
Contractual date of delivery	31 Dec 2021 (M16)
Actual date of delivery	21 Dec 2021 (M16)
Actual date of resubmission	28 June 2022 (M22)
Document status	Working document, pilot
Document version	v2
Online access	
Diffusion	Public (PU)
Nature of deliverable	Ration calculation table (MS Excel tool)
Work package	WP6
Partner responsible	University of Kassel
Author(s)	Regina Roessler, Eva Schlecht (UNI KASSEL)
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Keywords	Shrub foliage, ruminant feeding, ration calculation
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I. Executive summary

This report pertains to Task 6.2 “Implementing best foliage feeding strategies” and describes a pilot ration calculation table that will be used to elaborate shrub-foliage containing diets that meet the animals’ nutritional and, if feasible, nutraceutical requirements. The presented ration calculation table is a working document that will be continuously updated based on field tests and feedback from the target groups in the partner countries. The overall aim is to develop a flexible ration calculation tool for multiple ruminant livestock species, animal categories and breeds, as well as for various feeding strategies.

The final ration calculation table is meant to be used by national extension services, veterinarians, NGOs, and private feed consultants in the partner countries, to advice livestock keepers on how to formulate a balanced feed ration to reduce dietary imbalances between protein and energy supply of livestock in sub-Saharan Africa and to offer adequate amounts of feed to their animals. Feeding in line with animals’ requirements also reduces the excretion of unutilized nutrients, especially of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P), via the animals’ feces and urine. This in turn reduces nutrient losses and pollution of soil, groundwater (WP5) and air, and makes more nutrients available for optimal plant growth (WP4).

2. Description of the ration calculation table

Previous research revealed severe oversupply of nitrogen to livestock and dietary imbalances between their protein and energy supply in smallholder farming systems of sub-Saharan Africa. This leads to suboptimal feed utilization at the individual animal level, and therefore reduces biological and economic performances of livestock production systems [1]. To address these problems, farmers must receive appropriate information about feed quality and ration formulation. Available feed ration calculators do not consider the feeding of tropical shrub and tree foliage (e.g. Clemson Feed Ration Calculator [2], Advantage Feeders Ration Calculator [3]), and are mostly developed for intensive farming conditions focusing on one livestock species and modern livestock breeds in industrialized countries (e.g. AHDB Beef Ration Calculator [4], EZ Ration Processor Feed Ration Calculator [5]). There is one feed ration calculator that has been developed for farmers in developing countries, namely the Feedcalculator app [6], however, it only calculates feed recipes for chicken (broilers and layers), pigs, catfish and tilapia. Another limitation of available feed ration calculators is that they expect knowledge on the nutritional composition of feeds (Advantage Feeders Ration Calculator, AHDB Beef Ration Calculator, EZ Ration Feed Ration Processor Feed Ration Calculator). Furthermore, most calculators require a stable internet connection (Clemson Feed Ration Calculator, Advantage Feeders Ration Calculator, EZ Ration Processor Feed Ration Calculator), or an Android device (Feedcalculator app), while their use offline on a personal computer with Excel software is largely limited (AHDB Beef Ration Calculator). Finally, most of the feed ration calculators are in English language. There is one French feed ration calculator that has been developed for dairy cattle by Evalis [7], but the online application does not start due to a programming error (Fig. 1). Another French feed ration calculator (Altrop) has been developed for tropical cattle breeds on small-scale family farms in Burkina Faso considering locally available feedstuff [8], but the Excel calculator is not accessible online nor can it be downloaded from the web.

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Figure 1: Screenshot of the erratic start of the online French language feed ration calculator of Evialis

Hence, WP6 developed a ration calculation table for shrub foliage in MS Excel that goes beyond currently existing feed ration calculators and offers a menu in French language. The overall aim was to develop a flexible ration calculation tool for multiple ruminant livestock species (cattle, sheep, goats), multiple animal categories (growing males and females, adult males, as well as lactating, gestating and other adult females), and multiple (West-African) livestock breeds. The ration calculation procedures consider the energy and crude protein requirements for maintenance, growth, gestation, and walking of individual animals according to their breed and physiological status. Furthermore, the final tool will allow evaluating various feeding strategies, e.g. individual or group feeding, as well as homestead feeding or grazing. It will also consider results of the participatory rural appraisal (PRA) implemented by WVP2, and recommendations for locally adoptable integrated crop-shrub-livestock (CSL) systems that can improve soil quality and productivity (WVP4, WVP5), soil biological, chemical and physical functioning), as well as water availability, and crop yields (WVP5). The final ration calculation table is meant to be used by national extension services, veterinarians, NGOs, and private feed consultants in the partner countries, to advice livestock keepers to formulate a balanced feed ration based on the nutritional details of locally available feedstuffs and their animals' energy and crude protein requirements, that allows to improve livestock productivity, reduce feed and nutrient (N, P) wastage, and contribute to the maintenance or improvement of soil fertility and productivity as well as crop yields.

The first version of the ration calculation table that is presented here was developed for the feeding experiments of WP6 that are currently conducted on the research stations in Dahra/Senegal (CRZ), Katibougou/Mali (IPR) and Saria/Burkina Faso (INERA). In these feeding experiments, sheep's preferences for different shrub foliage and effects of shrub foliage on the rations' digestibility are evaluated (Task 6.2). Furthermore, the decomposition and nutrient release patterns of leaves from tree and shrub species, as well as foliage-derived animal manure is continuously assessed in litterbag experiments on the research stations in Dahra, Koulikoro and Saria (Task 6.3). The present version of the ration calculation table serves as pilot and is a working document. Updates and new features will be provided at regular times. Field tests

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and feedback by people from the mentioned target groups and from the innovation platforms within SustainSahel are planned, first field tests are scheduled for early 2022 in Senegal.

The description of the pilot ration calculation table follows the structure in MS Excel, which is as follows: The ration calculations are performed in the Excel sheet "**RationCalculation**". This sheet is locked for the user, no intervention by the user on this sheet is necessary. The same applies for the sheet "**Feedstuffs**" where the nutritional details of individual feedstuffs are stored that are needed for the calculation of the nutritional details of the total ration, as well as the feed intake of each animal. The interventions of the user are needed on sheet "**InputData**" where s/he provides input variables that are needed to perform the ration calculation. On sheet "**out_Checks**", the suggested rations are evaluated based on the DM intake capacity of each sheep and the ruminal nitrogen balance of the feed rations. In case that the given threshold values are exceeded, the user needs to adjust the ration. Finally, the daily amount of each feedstuff that has to be offered to cover the energy requirements of each animal is summarized on sheet "**out_FeedOffer**". In the following, the structure of the pilot ration calculation table, the general assumptions and equations are described more in detail.

2.1. Ration calculation

The pilot ration calculation table calculates rations for individual animals. For the ration calculation, the energy requirements of individual animals and the nutrient composition of the ration are considered. According to [1], the requirements of metabolizable energy for maintenance (Req ME_m) of an adult male sheep are assumed to be 474 kilojoules per kg metabolic weight (MW) and day (kJ/kg MW*d). The MW is the body weight (kg) scaled to the power of 0.75 (kg^{0.75}) [9]. The following equation is used to calculate the daily Req ME_m of each sheep in Megajoule (MJ):

$$\text{Eq. (1): Req ME}_m \text{ (MJ/d)} = \text{Req ME}_m \text{ (kJ/kg}^{0.75}\text{*d)} / 1000 * \text{MW (kg}^{0.75}\text{)}$$

The nutrient composition of the ration comprises the dry matter (DM) content per kilogram fresh matter (FM) (DM/kg FM), the metabolizable energy (ME) content (MJ/kg DM), the crude protein (CP) content (g/kg DM), the utilizable crude protein (uCP) content (g/kg DM), the rumen nitrogen balance (RNB) (g/kg DM) and the microbial protein (MP) (g/kg DM) of each feed type. uCP is calculated as

$$\text{Eq. (2): uCP (g/kg DM)} = \text{Microbial protein (MP) (g/kg DM)} + \text{CP (g/kg DM)} * 0.25, \text{ with}$$

$$\text{Eq. (3): MP (g/kg DM)} = \text{ME (MJ/kg DM)} * 10.3 \text{ (g/MJ ME)} [10].$$

RNB is calculated according to [11] using

$$\text{Eq. (4): [CP (g/kg DM) - uCP (g/kg DM)] * 0.16.}$$

The pilot ration calculation tool considers a single browse and a single staple feedstuff for the feed formulation. For the concentrate feed, a single concentrate feedstuff or a mix of up to three concentrate feedstuffs can be defined. Based on the proportion and the nutrient composition of each individual feed type, the nutrient composition of the total ration is calculated for each animal.

The metabolizable energy content of the ration (Ration ME) and the Req ME_m are used to calculate the quantity of feed that is needed to cover 1.2 times the Req ME_m of each individual sheep, plus a user defined surcharge to account for feed losses. For the total daily DM intake (DMI), Eq. (5) is used:

$$\text{Eq. (5): DMI (g/d)} = 1.2 * \text{Req ME}_m \text{ (MJ/kg DM)} / \text{Ration ME (MJ/d)} * 1000$$

The DMI for each feed type is then calculated by multiplying the total DMI (g/d) by the proportion of the browse, staple and concentrate feed in the ration. Finally, the FM intake (FMI) is obtained by dividing the DMI of each feed type by its DM content.

2.2. Feedstuffs

Thus far, the feedstuffs that are considered in the ration calculation table include those feedstuffs that have been selected for the current feeding experiments of WVP6 (Task 6.2). In general, three feed types are differentiated for the ration formulation: (a) shrub foliage, (b) staple, and (c) concentrate feed. Thirteen browse species (*Acacia tortilis* subsp. *raddiana*, *Adansonia digitata*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Balanites aegyptiaca*, *Bombax costatum*, *Entada africana*, *Ficus sycomorus*, *Guiera senegalensis*, *Khaya senegalensis*, *Lannea acida*, *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, *Pterocarpus lucens*, *Ziziphus jujuba*), two staple feedstuffs (wild grasses hay, *Pennisetum pedicellatum* hay) and four concentrate feedstuffs (*Faidherbia albida* pods, wheat bran, cassava peels and cotton seed cake) are included. The browse species represent the most available and preferred woody fodder according to the perception of agropastoralists in Yilou and Saria (Burkina Faso), Dahra and Ouarkhokh (Senegal), and Koulikoro (Mali), according to a survey conducted within WVP6 (see D6.1 Review report). Wild grasses and *Pennisetum pedicellatum* hay, *Faidherbia albida* pods and wheat bran are common livestock feeds in the SustainSahel study regions. In addition, cassava peels and cotton seed cake are included as concentrate feedstuffs due to their high energy and low protein content (only cassava peels). They may replace other concentrate feedstuffs in case of an energy deficit (in case that dry matter intake capacity of >3.5% of the body weight is exceeded but energy requirements are not met) or a highly negative rumen nitrogen balance (RNB is less than -10 g/d) of the ration.

The dry matter (DM), metabolizable energy (ME), crude protein (CP) and neutral-detergent fiber (NDF) content of the feedstuffs were taken from literature of a previous literature study (see D6.1 Review report on the utility of regionally and culturally important shrub foliage as animal feed complement) or from Feedipedia [12]. In the case that more than one value was found for a nutrient variable, the arithmetic mean was calculated. The nutrient composition of the selected feedstuffs and their respective sources are summarized in Table I.

Table I Nutrient composition of feedstuffs considered in the pilot ration calculation table

Feed type	DM (g/kg FM)	ME (MJ/kg DM)	CP (g/kg DM)	NDF (g/kg DM)	Source
(a) Shrub foliage					
<i>Acacia tortilis</i> subsp. <i>raddiana</i>	559	10.7	90	260	[12-14]
<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	327	11.2	109	357	[12,15]
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	500	8.1	222	373	[12,16]
<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>	479	7.8	95	296	[14,17,18]
<i>Bombax costatum</i> ¹	438	9.1	187	na	[19]
<i>Entada africana</i>	481	9.9	182	500	[20,21]
<i>Ficus sycomorus</i>	426	10.5	175	490	[22-24]
<i>Guiera senegalensis</i> ²	548	10.6	114	604	[25]
<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	500	7.9	106	514	[26,27]
<i>Lannea acida</i> ²	500	9.4	59	341	[28]
<i>Pterocarpus erinaceus</i>	545	8.1	139	507	[17,22,26-28]
<i>Pterocarpus lucens</i>	549	8.3	152	486	[22,25,29]

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<i>Ziziphus jujuba</i>	500	6.5	78	290	[14,17,28]
(b) Staple feed					
Wild grasses hay	971	6.9	33	760	[30]
<i>Pennisetum pedicellatum</i> hay	880	6.6	40	788	[12]
(c) Concentrate feed					
<i>Faidherbia albida</i> pods	921	12.5	110	429	[12]
Wheat bran	870	11.0	173	452	[12]
Cassava chips	876	12.2	29	514	[12]
Cotton seed cake	919	12.1	315	491	[25,30]

¹ Arithmetic mean of metabolizable energy values of all other shrub foliage; ² Metabolizable energy (ME) calculated as ME = Digestible organic matter (DOM) percentage * 0.15 according to [31], cited in [32]

2.3. User-defined input variables

For the calculation of animals' Req ME_m and the rations' nutritional details, the user has to provide animal- and diet-related variables that are described in the following sections.

2.3.1 Animal-related variables

The user has to provide the ID and the body weight of each animal. The body weight is needed for the calculation of the animal's MW which determines its Req ME_m. Furthermore, s/he has to select the diet (treatment) of each animal from a predefined dropdown list. In total, eight animals (Animal1-Animal8) and four treatments (Control, Treatment1, Treatment2, Treatment3) can be defined (Table 2).

Table 2 Input table for animal-related input variables to be defined by the user (coloured cells)

	ID	Liveweight (kg)	Treatment
Animal1	3098	16.20	Control
Animal2	3094	15.95	Control
Animal3	3093	17.58	Treatment1
Animal4	3099	16.28	Treatment1
Animal5	3100	15.73	Treatment2
Animal6	667	15.88	Treatment2
Animal7	668	16.88	Treatment3
Animal8	673	17.53	Treatment3

2.3.2 Diet-related variables

Along the animal-related variables, the user has to provide information on the four treatments, namely the feedstuffs used as shrub foliage, staple, and concentrate feed, and their shares in each treatment. The feedstuffs have to be selected from a predefined dropdown list that contains various feedstuffs for each of the three feed types (shrub foliage, staple, concentrate). Generally, one shrub foliage, one staple and up to three concentrate feedstuffs can be defined for each treatment, except for animals in the control group that do not receive any shrub foliage (Table 3). The list of feedstuffs will be continuously updated and new feedstuffs will be added.

Table 3 Input table for feedtypes to be selected by the user for each feed type (coloured cells)

Treatment	Shrub foliage	Staple	Concentrate 1	Concentrate 2	Concentrate 3
Control		Wild grasses hay	<i>Faidherbia albida</i> pods		
Treatment1	<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	Wild grasses hay	<i>Faidherbia albida</i> pods		
Treatment2	<i>Ficus sycomorus</i>	Wild grasses hay	<i>Faidherbia albida</i> pods		
Treatment3	<i>Bombax costatum</i>	Wild grasses hay	<i>Faidherbia albida</i> pods		

In the next step, the user has to provide the shares of the shrub foliage, staple and concentrate feeds. The share of the shrub foliage is 0.3 and the share for the concentrate mix should be max. 0.25. The latter is calculated from the shares of the single concentrate feedstuffs that have been selected by the user in the previous step. The shares of the three feed types should sum up to 1.0 (Table 4). Warnings will be automatically displayed in case that the share of the shrub foliage is unequal to 0.3, that the concentrate mix share exceeds 0.25 and/or the sum of total shares exceeds 1.0.

Table 4 Input table for shares to be defined for each feed type (coloured cells)

Animal_ID	Treatment	Shrub foliage	Staple	Concentrate 1	Concentrate 2	Concentrate 3	Concentrate mix	Total
3098	Control	0	0.75	0.25			0.25	1.00
3094	Control	0	0.75	0.25			0.25	1.00
3093	Treatment1	0.3	0.45	0.25			0.25	1.00
3099	Treatment1	0.3	0.45	0.25			0.25	1.00
3100	Treatment2	0.3	0.45	0.25			0.25	1.00
667	Treatment2	0.3	0.45	0.25			0.25	1.00
668	Treatment3	0.3	0.45	0.25			0.25	1.00
673	Treatment3	0.3	0.45	0.25			0.25	1.00

Finally, the user can define a surcharge to each feed type to account for feed losses. We suggest 5-10% surcharge to reduce feed wastage.

3. Dissemination activities related with the Deliverable

The present version of the ration calculation table is an internal working document. Field tests and feedback by national extension services, veterinarians, NGOs and private field consultants, as well as from the innovation platforms within SustainSahel, will be conducted to continuously update and further elaborate the ration calculation table according to the needs of the target groups. First field tests are scheduled for early 2022 in Senegal.

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4. Appendix

The pilot MS Excel ration calculation tool is available as an excel file which is a dynamic and workable tool where inputs can be entered and calculations obtained. For technical purposes we are providing screenshots of the different tables of the file in this appendix.

Sheet 1: InputData

1. Insert ID, liveweight and diet of each animal.					N.B.: Only fill the colored cells.	
	ID	Liveweight (kg)	Treatment	Browse		
Animal1	3098	16.20	Control			
Animal2	3094	15.95	Control			
Animal3	3093	17.58	Treatment1	Khaya senegalensis		
Animal4	3099	16.28	Treatment1	Khaya senegalensis		
Animal5	3100	15.73	Treatment2	Ficus sycomorus		
Animal6	667	15.88	Treatment2	Ficus sycomorus		
Animal7	668	16.88	Treatment3	Bombax costatum		
Animal8	673	17.53	Treatment3	Bombax costatum		

2. Select browse species, staple feed and concentrate feed from dropdown list and list the concentrate feeds in the right table only feed cassava chips if the intake of staple feed is very low and the DMI capacity is > 3.5%					
Treatment	Shrub foliage	Staple	Concentrate 1	Concentrate 2	Concentrate 3
Control		Wild grasses hay	Faidherbia albida pods		
Treatment1	Khaya senegal	Wild grasses hay	Faidherbia albida pods		
Treatment2	Ficus sycomori	Wild grasses hay	Faidherbia albida pods		
Treatment3	Bombax costa	Wild grasses hay	Faidherbia albida pods		

3. Insert ratio of browse, staple and concentrate feeds (ratio for concentrate mix is calculated, should be max. 0.25)								
Animal_ID	Treatment	Shrub foliage	Staple	Concentrate 1	Concentrate 2	Concentrate 3	Concentrate mix	Total
3098	Control	0	0.75	0.25			0.25	1.00
3094	Control	0	0.75	0.25			0.25	1.00
3093	Treatment1	0.3	0.45	0.25			0.25	1.00
3099	Treatment1	0.3	0.45	0.25			0.25	1.00
3100	Treatment2	0.3	0.45	0.25			0.25	1.00
667	Treatment2	0.3	0.45	0.25			0.25	1.00
668	Treatment3	0.3	0.45	0.25			0.25	1.00
673	Treatment3	0.3	0.45	0.25			0.25	1.00

4. Surcharge to account for feed losses	
Surcharge	0.1

Sheet 2: out_Checks

1. DM intake capacity (maximum 3.5% of the liveweight)						if DMI / kg liveweight >3.5% then replace 50%-100% of the concentrate feed by cassava peels	
Animal	Treatment	Shrub foliage	DMI (g/d)	Liveweight (kg)	DMI (kg)/ Liveweight (kg)		
3098	Control		553	16.20	3.4		
3094	Control		547	15.95	3.4		
3093	Treatment1	Khaya senegalensis	568	17.58	3.2		
3099	Treatment1	Khaya senegalensis	536	16.28	3.3		
3100	Treatment2	Ficus sycomorus	478	15.73	3.0		
667	Treatment2	Ficus sycomorus	482	15.88	3.0		
668	Treatment3	Bombax costatum	529	16.88	3.1		
673	Treatment3	Bombax costatum	544	17.53	3.1		

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2. RNB (g/d) (threshold value -10 g/d?)			
Animal	Treatment	Shrub foliage	RNB (g N/d)
3098	Control		-4.10
3094	Control		-4.05
3093	Treatment1	Khaya senegalensis	-2.99
3099	Treatment1	Khaya senegalensis	-2.83
3100	Treatment2	Ficus sycomorus	-1.96
667	Treatment2	Ficus sycomorus	-1.98
668	Treatment3	Bombax costatum	-1.56
673	Treatment3	Bombax costatum	-1.61

Sheet 3: out_FeedOffer

Feed offer per day and sheep (1.2 maintenance requirements + surcharge to account for feed losses)								
Animal_ID	Treatment	Shrub foliage	Browse feed offered DM as fed (g/d)	Staple feed DM as fed (g/d)	Concentrate mix DM as fed (g/d)	Concentrate 1 DM as fed (g/20d)	Concentrate 2 DM as fed (g/20d)	Concentrate 3 DM as fed (g/20d)
3098	Control			456.5	152.2	152.2	0.0	0.0
3094	Control			451.2	150.4	150.4	0.0	0.0
3093	Treatment1	Khaya senegalensis	187.3	281.0	156.1	156.1	0.0	0.0
3099	Treatment1	Khaya senegalensis	176.9	265.3	147.4	147.4	0.0	0.0
3100	Treatment2	Ficus sycomorus	157.8	236.7	131.5	131.5	0.0	0.0
667	Treatment2	Ficus sycomorus	158.9	238.4	132.5	132.5	0.0	0.0
668	Treatment3	Bombax costatum	174.4	261.6	145.4	145.4	0.0	0.0
673	Treatment3	Bombax costatum	179.4	269.2	149.5	149.5	0.0	0.0
Surcharge		10 %						

Sheet 4: RationCalculation

1. Nutrient composition of feed rations (based on ratios of feedstuffs)								
Animal_ID	Treatment							
3098	Control							
Feed type	Feedstuffs	Ratio in diet	DM (g/kg FM)	ME (MJ/kg DM)	CP (g/kg DM)	uCP (g/kg DM)	RNB (g/kg DM)	MP (g/kg DM)
Browse		0.00						
Staple	Wild grasses hay	0.75	971	6.9	33	79.3	-7.41	71.1
Concentrate 1	Faidherbia albida pod	0.25	921	12.5	110	156.3	-7.40	128.8
Concentrate 2		0.00						
Concentrate 3		0.00						
Total ration		1.00	959	8.3	52	98.6	-7.41	85.5
3094	Control							
Feed type	Feedstuffs	Ratio in diet	DM (g/kg FM)	ME (MJ/kg DM)	CP (g/kg DM)	uCP (g/kg DM)	RNB (g/kg DM)	MP (g/kg DM)
Browse		0.00						
Staple	Wild grasses hay	0.75	971	6.9	33	79.3	-7.41	71.1
Concentrate 1	Faidherbia albida pod	0.25	921	12.5	110	156.3	-7.40	128.8
Concentrate 2		0.00						
Concentrate 3		0.00						
Total ration		1.00	959	8.3	52	98.6	-7.41	85.5
3093	Treatment1							

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Feed type	Feedstuffs	Ratio in diet	DM (g/kg FM)	ME (MJ/kg DM)	CP (g/kg DM)	uCP (g/kg DM)	RNB (g/kg DM)	MP (g/kg DM)
Browse	Khaya senegalensis	0.30	500	7.9	106	107.9	-0.30	81.4
Staple	Wild grasses hay	0.45	971	6.9	33	79.3	-7.41	71.1
Concentrate 1	Faidherbia albida pod	0.25	921	12.5	110	156.3	-7.40	128.8
Concentrate 2		0.00						
Concentrate 3		0.00						
Total ration		1.00	817	8.6	74	107.1	-5.27	88.6

Animal_ID	Treatment
3099	Treatment1

Feed type	Feedstuffs	Ratio in diet	DM (g/kg FM)	ME (MJ/kg DM)	CP (g/kg DM)	uCP (g/kg DM)	RNB (g/kg DM)	MP (g/kg DM)
Browse	Khaya senegalensis	0.30	500	7.9	106	107.9	-0.30	81.4
Staple	Wild grasses hay	0.45	971	6.9	33	79.3	-7.41	71.1
Concentrate 1	Faidherbia albida pod	0.25	921	12.5	110	156.3	-7.40	128.8
Concentrate 2		0.00						
Concentrate 3		0.00						
Total ration		1.00	817	8.6	74	107.1	-5.27	88.6

Animal_ID	Treatment
3100	Treatment2

Feed type	Feedstuffs	Ratio in diet	DM (g/kg FM)	ME (MJ/kg DM)	CP (g/kg DM)	uCP (g/kg DM)	RNB (g/kg DM)	MP (g/kg DM)
Browse	Ficus sycomorus	0.30	426	10.5	175	152.2	3.59	108.6
Staple	Wild grasses hay	0.45	971	6.9	33	79.3	-7.41	71.1
Concentrate 1	Faidherbia albida pod	0.25	921	12.5	110	156.3	-7.40	128.8
Concentrate 2		0.00						
Concentrate 3		0.00						
Total ration		1.00	795	9.4	95	120.4	-4.11	96.7

Animal_ID	Treatment
667	Treatment2

Feed type	Feedstuffs	Ratio in diet	DM (g/kg FM)	ME (MJ/kg DM)	CP (g/kg DM)	uCP (g/kg DM)	RNB (g/kg DM)	MP (g/kg DM)
Browse	Ficus sycomorus	0.3	426	10.5	175	152.2	3.59	108.6
Staple	Wild grasses hay	0.45	971	6.9	33	79.3	-7.41	71.1
Concentrate 1	Faidherbia albida pod	0.25	921	12.5	110	156.3	-7.40	128.8
Concentrate 2		0						
Concentrate 3		0						
Total ration		1.00	795	9.4	95	120.4	-4.11	96.7

Animal_ID	Treatment
668	Treatment3

Feed type	Feedstuffs	Ratio in diet	DM (g/kg FM)	ME (MJ/kg DM)	CP (g/kg DM)	uCP (g/kg DM)	RNB (g/kg DM)	MP (g/kg DM)
Browse	Bombax costatum	0.3	438	9.1	187	140.5	7.44	93.7
Staple	Wild grasses hay	0.45	971	6.9	33	79.3	-7.41	71.1
Concentrate 1	Faidherbia albida pod	0.25	921	12.5	110	156.3	-7.40	128.8
Concentrate 2		0						
Concentrate 3		0						
Total ration		1.00	799	9.0	98	116.9	-2.95	92.3

Animal_ID	Treatment
673	Treatment3

Feed type	Feedstuffs	Ratio in diet	DM (g/kg FM)	ME (MJ/kg DM)	CP (g/kg DM)	uCP (g/kg DM)	RNB (g/kg DM)	MP (g/kg DM)
Browse	Bombax costatum	0.3	438	9.1	187	140.5	7.44	93.7
Staple	Wild grasses hay	0.45	971	6.9	33	79.3	-7.41	71.1
Concentrate 1	Faidherbia albida pod	0.25	921	12.5	110	156.3	-7.40	128.8
Concentrate 2		0						
Concentrate 3		0						
Total ration		1.00	799	9.0	98	116.9	-2.95	92.3

2. ME requirements of animals

Animal	Treatment	Liveweight (kg)	Metabolic liveweight (kg ^{0.75})	ME requirements (kJ/kg ^{0.75} /d)	ME requirements (MJ/d)	1.2*ME requirements (MJ/d)	1.5*ME requirements (MJ/d)
3098	Control	16.2	8.1	474	3.8	4.6	5.7
3094	Control	16.0	8.0	474	3.8	4.5	5.7
3093	Treatment1	17.6	8.6	474	4.1	4.9	6.1
3099	Treatment1	16.3	8.1	474	3.8	4.6	5.8
3100	Treatment2	15.7	7.9	474	3.7	4.5	5.6
667	Treatment2	15.9	8.0	474	3.8	4.5	5.7
668	Treatment3	16.9	8.3	474	3.9	4.7	5.9
673	Treatment3	17.5	8.6	474	4.1	4.9	6.1

D6.2 Ration calculation table

3. Feed rations of animals													
1.2 maintenance feeding													
Animal	Diet	Ration ME (MJ/kg DM)	DMI (g/d)	FMI Browse (g/d)	FMI Staple (g/d)	FMI Concentrate 1 (g/d)	FMI Concentrate 2 (g/d)	FMI Concentrate 3 (g/d)	uCP (g/d)	CP (g/d)	RNB (g N/d)	RNB (% Total N)	MP (g/d)
3098	Control	8.3	553.4		427.4	150.2			54.5	28.9	-4.10	-88.62	47.3
3094	Control	8.3	547.0		422.5	148.5			53.9	28.6	-4.05	-88.62	46.8
3093	Treatment1	8.6	567.7	340.6	263.1	154.1			60.8	42.1	-2.99	-44.46	50.3
3099	Treatment1	8.6	535.9	321.6	248.4	145.5			57.4	39.7	-2.83	-44.46	47.5
3100	Treatment2	9.4	478.2	336.8	221.6	129.8			57.6	45.3	-1.96	-27.10	46.3
667	Treatment2	9.4	481.7	339.2	223.2	130.7			58.0	45.6	-1.98	-27.10	46.6
668	Treatment3	9.0	528.5	362.0	245.0	143.5			61.8	52.0	-1.56	-18.74	48.8
673	Treatment3	9.0	543.7	372.4	252.0	147.6			63.6	53.5	-1.61	-18.74	50.2

Animal	Diet	Ration ME (MJ/kg DM)	DMI (g/d)	DMI Browse (g/d)	DMI Staple (g/d)	DMI Concentrate 1 (g/d)	DMI Concentrate 2 (g/d)	DMI Concentrate 3 (g/d)
3098	Control	8.3	553.4		415.0	138.3		
3094	Control	7.9	547.0	0.0	410.2	136.7		
3093	Treatment1	8.6	567.7	170.3	255.3	141.9		
3099	Treatment1	8.6	535.9	160.8	241.2	134.0		
3100	Treatment2	9.4	478.2	143.5	215.2	119.6		
667	Treatment2	9.4	481.7	144.5	216.7	120.4		
668	Treatment3	9.0	528.5	158.6	237.8	132.1		
673	Treatment3	9.0	543.7	163.1	244.7	135.9		

Sheet 5: FeedStuffs

Browse species / shrub foliage	Source	DM (g/kg FM)	ME (MJ/kg DM)	CP (g/kg DM)	NDF (g/kg DM)	Abbreviations
Acacia tortilis subsp. raddiana (syn. Acacia raddiana)	[12,13,17]	559	10.7	90	260	DM Dry matter
Adansonia digitata	[12,15]	327	11.2	109	357	FM Fresh matter
Azadirachta indica	[12,16]	500	8.1	222	373	CP Crude protein
Balanites aegyptiaca	[8,17,18]	479	7.8	95	296	ME Metabolizable energy
Bombax costatum	[19]	438	9.1	187	na	
Entada africana	[1,21]	481	9.9	182	500	
Ficus sycomorus	[2,3,4]	426	10.5	175	490	
Guiera senegalensis	[20]; ME=DOM*0.15	548	10.6	114	604	
Khaya senegalensis	[5,6]	500	7.9	106	514	
Lannea acida (syn. Lannea microcarpa)	[9]; ME=DOM*0.15	500	9.4	59	341	
Pterocarpus erinaceus	[2,5,6,8,9]	545	8.1	139	507	
Pterocarpus lucens	[2,10,20]	549	8.3	152	486	
Ziziphus jujuba (syn. Ziziphus mauritiana)	[8,9,17]	500	6.5	78	290	
Staple feed						
Wild grasses hay	[11]	971	6.9	33	760	
Pennisetum pedicellatum hay	[12]	880	6.6	40	788	
Concentrate feed						
Faidherbia albida pods	[12]	921	12.5	110	429	
Wheat bran	[12]	870	11.0	173	452	
Cassava chips	[12]	876	12.2	29	514	
Cotton seed cake	[11,20]	919	12.1	315	491	

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